

Dry Electrodes in Non-Invasive Electrophysiology – A Review

Anjula C. De Silva

Department of Electronic and Telecommunication Engineering, University of Moratuwa

Katubedda, Sri Lanka

Phone: +94-112-650-301 Fax: +94-112-650-622 E-mail: anjulads@uom.lk

1. Introduction

Electrophysiology is a well-established clinical tool for diagnosing disorders associated with the nervous system. In addition, it shows promising applications in brain-computer/machine-interfacing and controlling prosthetics. However, this technology suffers from following limitations when converting the laboratory success into widespread use.

- i. Skin-electrode interface
- ii. Electrode-hardware interfacing circuit

This article intends to review the solutions that have been implemented thus far and indicated the way forward to achieve the widespread use of this technology.

2. Electrodes

Categorization of non-invasive electrodes

Non-invasive electrodes can be broadly categorized into wet and dry electrodes as shown in Fig. 1. The types of dry electrodes that are currently used are; Surface contact electrodes, Penetrating electrodes and Non-contact electrodes.

Fig. 1 - Categorization of non-invasive electrodes

At present, the benchmark in electrophysiology is the gel-based Ag/AgCl wet electrode. Even though this has excellent signal integrity with a low skin-to-electrode impedance, it suffers from; long setup time, short-term use (few hours due to dehydration of the gel), inconvenience and skin irritations. Therefore, a shift of the electrode technology from wet electrodes to dry electrodes is essential [1].

Titanium (Ti) and nanotechnology based dry electrodes

Use of biocompatible Ti as a base material for electrodes has shown promising results with the surface coated with titanium nitride

(TiN) which is unaffected by sweat [2]. Fiedler P. et. al. reports on a Ti/TiN EEG electrode with a tip diameter of 1.5 mm spring mounted on a pneumatically suspended holder to enhance the contact with the skin [3]. EEG results showed no significant difference in the power spectral density and time domain activity between dry Ti/TiN and wet Ag/AgCl electrodes.

A semi-dry EEG electrode based on micro-porous Ti has been proposed by Peng H.L. et. al. has produced comparable results to that of a standard wet Ag/AgCl with the additional advantage of long term use [4]. A 200 µl 0.9% NaCl solution was used as the electrolyte stored in a polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) compartment attached on top of the electrode as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 - Micro-porous Ti electrode with the PDMS compartment [4]

Nanotechnology based electrodes are getting more attention due to good wearability, better contact with the curvilinear surface of the skin and reduced motion artifacts [5]. Nanowires made out of Ag, Pt, Au are a promising method of integrating electrodes into textile with the added advantage of high resistance to machine washing [6]. Carbon nanotubes (CNT) are the other promising technology due to high mechanical strength, good electrical conductivity and the ability to mass produced at a relatively low cost [5]. Lee S.M. et. al. mixed CNT with adhesive PDMS which reduced relative movements of the electrodes by sticking it on to the skin even within wrinkles as shown in Fig. 3 reducing motion artifacts [7].

Fig. 3 - Scanning electron microscopy image of a CNT/adhesive PDMS electrode attached to a skin replica [7]

Minimally invasive penetrating electrodes with CNT have also been explored yielding enhanced signal integrity. Ruffin G. et. al. has reported the use of CVD-grown, multiwalled CNT forest as an electrode which penetrated the stratum corneum to a depth of 10-15 μm [8]. However, an important feature here is the in-situ amplification as shown in Fig. 4 which minimizes the effect of noise.

Fig. 4 - Penetrating CNT based dry electrode [8]

3. Interfacing circuit

The interfacing circuit from the electrode to the amplifier is vital in acquiring a low noise electrophysiological signal especially in the case of EEG signals which are less than 10 μV . According to the placement and the functionality of this interfacing circuits, the electrode is categorized into 1) passive electrode 2) active electrode (AE) or 3) digital active electrode (DAE) (see concept illustrations in Fig. 5). Passive electrodes are the conventional type where the instrumentation amplifier (IA) and the analog to digital conversion (ADC) at a central unit detached from the body. To overcome the noise added along the conducting wires, the pre-amplification of the biosignal is performed at the electrode in an AE. The DAE converts the pre-amplified signal to the digital domain before transmitting it to the central microcontroller (MCU) further reducing noise contamination.

Fig. 5 - Types of electrode interfacing circuits (a) Passive electrode (b) Active electrode (c) Digital active electrode

Realizing AEs and DAEs are a challenging task due to the complex design, miniaturizing, power requirements and number of wires required [9]. Complexity of the design includes buffering amplifiers with a high input impedance ($\text{G}\Omega$ range), low output

impedance, simultaneous AC/DC coupling [10], electrode offset compensation, common mode rejection ratio enhancement using the common mode feedback method [11] or the common mode feedforward method [12].

Fabrication of AEs and DAEs

Inclusion of above mentioned features on to the electrode which of approximately 1 cm^2 is becoming the future of non-invasive electrophysiology. While there are only a limited number of attempts have been made in this regard, Xu J. et. al. claims successful fabrication of an AE [12] and then improving it to a DAE [13].

In the initial version, the AE and a separate backend with the 12-bit ADC supporting 8 channels was fabricated as shown in Fig. 6. Each EEG channel has a 1.2 $\text{G}\Omega$ input impedance (at 20 Hz), 1.75 μV_{rms} (0.5–100 Hz) input-referred noise, 84 dB CMRR and ± 250 mV electrode offset rejection capability. The EEG acquisition system was implemented in a standard 0.18 μm CMOS process, and consumed 48 μA per channel from a 1.8 V supply.

Fig. 6 - Fabricated AE and the Backend ADC [12]

In the improved second version, Xu J. et. al. combines the ADC with the AE creating a DAE supporting 15 channels of data to be transmitted to a central MCU via I²C. The DAE (shown in Fig. 7) was implemented in a standard 0.18 μm CMOS process, and occupies an area of 15.8 mm^2 . Each chip consumes 58 μA from a 1.8 V supply. Improving the pre-amplifier performance, the input referred noise was reduced to 0.65 μV_{rms} (0.5–100 Hz), CMRR increased to 102 dB and electrode offset rejection capability increased to ± 350 mV. However, the input impedance was also reduced to 1 $\text{G}\Omega$ at 1 Hz and 100 $\text{M}\Omega$ at 50 Hz.

Fig. 7 - Fabricated DAE [13]

4. Conclusion

Successful acquisition of non-invasive electrophysiological signals depends upon the skin-electrode interface and the electrode-hardware interfacing circuit. While nanotechnology based nanowires and carbon nanotubes show promise as dry electrodes, digital active electrodes show promise as an interfacing circuit with high resistance to noise contamination. Considering the miniaturizing and the low power consumption, DAEs require further research to optimize such parameters. Therefore, extensive involvement is required from the experts on semiconductor nanodevices.

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